

DEFORMATION MECHANISM INVESTIGATION FOR EPOXY BY IN-SITU ELECTRICAL AND MECHANICS COUPLING MEASUREMENT

Yinggang Miao¹, Chuanguo Ma² and Tiejun Wang³

¹ State Key Laboratory for Strength and Vibration of Mechanical Structures, Department of Engineering Mechanics, School of Aerospace Engineering, Xi'an Jiaotong University, Xi'an, Shaanxi 710049, China

² School of Material Science and Engineering, Guilin University of Electronic Technology, Guilin 541004, P. R. China

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ABSTRACT

The carbon nanotube modified composite is fabricated and experimentally measured by the electrical resistance of specimen during compressive loading to obtain the composite resistivity-strain curve, in the hope of probing into the deformation mechanism at peak stress. The deformation mechanism would change at the peak stress due to the sharp increase of specimen volume resistivity, which is also further confirmed by a series of specifically-designed experiments. Then the mechanism is proposed that while loading to peak stress, some cross-linked sites start to break, then induces the abrupt increase of material resistivity. And then the molecular chain units freed from the broken sites can form the molecular chain segments which facilitate to initiate the strain-softening deformation. The mechanism is also further confirmed by analysis on the gap stress, peak strain and CNT conductive mechanism. Such a mechanism bridges and modifies the previous consensus regarding the natures of below and post peak stress deformation of epoxy.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymeric materials are fundamental substances widely used in daily life. Like the epoxies, a popular class of polymers, are thermosetting polymers with linear or three dimensions cross-linked structures. Now, it has widely served as engineering materials in lightweight load-bearing applications, particularly in the aerospace industry, due to high specific strength and stiffness, excellent adhesion strength [1,2]. Then, their mechanical behaviors have been paid more attention by researchers from industrial and scientific committees with the aim to further reinforce them and extend their applications [3,4]. The intrinsic deformation mechanism is thus desired to be understood for it [5,6,7]. Concerning to the intrinsic mechanisms of deformation, cooperative motion of valence angles, and short chain links are corresponding to the deformation prior to the peak stress, and the chain segments start to move, accounting for the following strain softening deformation [8,9]. However, why the strain softening initiate beyond the peak stress for the glassy epoxy, is little information available. And what specifically happens in the molecular microstructures when the specimen was stressed to its peak stress, is also still not studied in details. Though the apparatuses based on X-ray scattering technique can conduct the real time monitoring of evolution of structure for polymeric materials during deformation, and achieve a better understanding of the physics in polymer science [10,11], they failed to detect the sub-nano structural evolutions. It is of great interest, indeed, to well know the molecular chain evolution mechanism within this process both for the physical-based constitutive model [3,8] to accurately character the features of materials, and to design specifically materials for functional materials for industries.

The in-situ electrical measurement is an effective method for materials health monitoring during loading process [12-15]. This can offer continuous electrical information of materials/structures, and be also more available for researchers than the X-ray scattering technique. Polymeric resins are usually further modified by adding nanoparticles, for achieving better mechanical and electrical properties, especially since carbon nanotube (short for CNT) has been discovered [16]. They are in the stage where the focus is more and more on their mechanical and electrical applications in polymer-matrix

composite, where carbon nanotube fillers can provide the missing property of the matrix [17-20]. The composites with CNT incorporation can open another door for probing into the potential mechanism and damage in mechanic view, by coupling electrical-mechanical measurement.

In this work, an in-situ coupling electrical-mechanical measurement system is designed and used to conduct the measurement of the electrical information of CNT composite specimen while compressive loading. The resistivity of CNT nanocomposite is obtained and analyzed for the deformation mechanism at peak stress. Then a series of the compressive experiments are specifically performed on pure epoxy specimen, aiming for probe into the potential mechanism at peak stress. Besides, the other mechanical behaviors of epoxy could also further confirm the mechanism.

2 MATERIALS AND SPECIMEN

Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy with an epoxide equivalent weight of 185 g/mol (E51) and the curing agent 593 are manufactured by Shanghai Resin Factory Co., Ltd. Carbon nanotube is introduced to fabricate epoxy-matrix composite. Pristine CVD-multi-walled carbon nanotubes (CNTs) with average diameter of 60 nm and average length of 3 μm are supplied by Chengdu Organic Chemicals Co. Ltd, China. 3g CNTs are dispersed in 100 g acetone by mechanical stirring for 15 min, followed by ultra-sonication for 30 min. Then 100 g epoxy (E51) is added to the suspension and mixed evenly. Then curing agent 593 is added into the suspensions and stirred for 5 minutes. Then the mixtures are poured into a polypropylene mold and cured at room temperature for 2 h, followed by another 4 h at 80 °C, then the CNT nanocomposite is fabricated. In addition, pure epoxy bulk is also fabricated. Finally, the bulks are cut into $\varnothing 4.0 \text{ mm} \times 4.0 \text{ mm}$ cylindrical specimens for mechanical experimental study.

3 EXPERIMENTS

The compression tests are conducted by using Micro-Instron 5848 machine. The crosshead velocity is controlled to achieve loading strain rate 0.001 s⁻¹. Firstly, electrical-mechanic coupling experiments are designed to conduct CNT reinforced composite. Then, a series of compression experiments are specifically designed on pure epoxy loaded to different strains, aiming for further investigating the mechanical characteristics.

3.1 Electric/mechanic coupling experiments on CNT nanocomposite

A synchronous measurement of specimen resistance is conducted by using a designed electric-mechanic coupling experiments system with the schematic map shown as Fig.1 (A), and CNT nanocomposite specimen is connected into the system shown as Fig.1 (B). The voltage E is 10 V, and the data acquisition device is used to record the output signal of specimen during deforming. In Fig.1 (B), two finely-fabricated glass pads are introduced to shield potential electrical interference from the conductive metal crossheads. The conductive lubricate is pasted between the specimen and pads to function both in minimizing the friction influence and contacting lead wires to the measurement system. Its resistivity is lower down to $1 \times 10^{-5} \sim 10^{-7} \Omega\text{m}$, thus the contacting resistance is in several Ω . The specimen resistance is in order of 10,000 Ω , and thus the contacting resistance can be neglected in formulating the resistance of specimen. And the experimental curves are displayed in Fig.2 (A) and (B).

Figure 1 Schematic map of specimen resistance measurement (A), and the experimental picture of compression test where the glass pads are used for shielding potential interference (B).

3.2 Below peak stress experiments on pure epoxy

Multi-times loading tests are performed on an epoxy specimen for three times with the maximum load below peak stress, quantitatively equaling to 0.990 times of the peak stress. Then the fourth and fifth tests are conducted to different large deformation, and the experimental curves are displayed in Fig.3 (A).

3.3 Over peak stress experiments on pure epoxy

An epoxy specimen is conducted for eight times with the applied load beyond the peak stress of the specimen by few. Then the ninth and tenth tests are further conducted to different large deformation, and the experimental curves are displayed in Fig.3 (B).

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Electric/mechanic behaviors around peak stress

The resistivity of specimen during deformation is deduced as Eq. 1, with the assumption of incompressive material volume.

$$R = \rho \frac{l}{S} \Rightarrow \rho = \frac{R \cdot S}{l} = \frac{R \cdot V}{l^2} = \frac{R \cdot V}{l_0^2 \cdot (1 - \varepsilon)} \quad (1)$$

where R is measured specimen resistance, ρ , l , S and V are volume resistivity, length, interface area and volume of specimen, respectively. And l_0 , ε are the initial length, true strain of specimen, respectively. The experimental results of CNT composite are shown in Fig.2, which displays the origin mechanical curve, the electrical resistance curve, the calculated true stress-strain curve and in-situ volume resistance curve of specimen during loading process, respectively. The stress-strain curve shares the similar mechanic behavior with other polymer materials [5,8]: it firstly deforms linearly and then comes in the nonlinear behavior, and achieves to the peak stress, followed by the strain-softening characteristics. It is demonstrated in Fig. 2(C) that with the strain continuing, the volume resistivity is gradually increasing and then sharply growing up. The fitted slope increases by about 2.89 times from

26.804 to 77.475 as indicated in Fig. 2(C). The crossing point for both fitted lines is nearly at the strain where the peak stress occurs. So, it is reasonable to predict that the deformation mechanism would change of the molecular microstructure at peak stress.

Figure 2 Origin experimental data of CNT composite under compressive loading: (A) load-displacement curve and (B) the corresponding specimen voltage signal, and calculated stress-strain curve and volume resistivity curve during deforming.

The stress strain curves are calculated of pure epoxy specimens under different loading, and shown in Figure 3. It is clear to find that the epoxy, like the CNT nanocomposites shown in Fig. 2 (C), shares same mechanical behaviors: it firstly deformed linearly elastically, and then come into nonlinear-elastically deformation, until to the peak stress, followed by the strain softening process. It is confirmed by the normalized stress-strain curves of them shown in Figure 4. It is well known that, the internal microstructure evolution acts decisive roles in the mechanical performance of the materials. Thus, they share the similar microstructural deformation around the peak stress.

Figure 3 Stress-strain curves of epoxy under different strains (A) with the previous three experiments

below peak stress, and (B) with the previous nine experiments over peak stress.

Figure 4 Normalized stress-strain curves characteristics of pure epoxy and CNT nanocomposite.

4.2 Deformation mechanism at peak stress

Elastic modulus of material is an essential parameter to assess its mechanical behavior, especially for the mechanical damage assessment. Thus, it is introduced to analyze the deformation characteristics. They are normalized by its elastic modulus in the first loading with the formulation shown in Equation 2, and displayed in Fig.5 (A) and (B) for below and over peak stress experiments, respectively.

$$E_{si} = \frac{E_{ith}}{E_1} \quad (2)$$

where E_1 is the elastic modulus of the first load for each specimen involved, and E_{si} was the specific elastic modulus of the i th load, with $i=2,3$, until to 10.

Figure 5 Specific elastic modulus comparisons for prior to, beyond peak stress.

Figure 5 shows the specific elastic modulus trends with the loading times under different loading amplitudes (namely, the below peak stress experiments and post peak stress experiments). With respect to the below peak stress experiments, there is little change in the previous 4 tests with the maximum stress up to 0.990 peaks stress, as shown in Figure 5(A). It can be concluded that the specimen deformation can nearly fully recover even though it was loaded into nonlinear deformation region and approached to the peak stress. And thus it is permitted to conclude that the deformation before the peak strain could be totally recoverable. In the 4th test, the specimen was loaded to plateau stress stage, the specific modulus sharply decreases to 0.69. The specimen would undergo deformations like the irreversible motion of molecular chains structures, especially in the strain softening stage. In Figure 5 (B), it shows that the specific elastic modulus decreases with loading times. For the previous nine tests, the modulus presents distinctly decreasing trends, even the specimen was loaded beyond its peak stress over a few strain as shown in Fig. 3 (B). It is noteworthy that the specific modulus in tenth experiment has been drop to 0.58. It is lower than 0.69 in Figure 5 (A).

It is demonstrated from Figure 4 that the stress strain curves of CNT composite and pure epoxy own similar mechanical characteristics, and share the same mechanism accounting for the peak stress deformation. For a densely crosslinking polymer, the crosslinking degree has a direct influence on the matrix mechanics [21-23]. Thus, it could be predicted that the crosslinking sites are about to break when the specimen is loaded to its peak stress, and the breaking of crosslinking sites initiate the subsequent strain softening. Then the chain segments start to move, charging for the following strain softening deformation. The evolution process is predicted in details as follows: when the external stress is applied to the three-dimension crosslinking epoxy, the bond length, valence angles, and other short chain units start to cooperative motion for the reversible deformation prior to the peak stress. With the deformation continuing up to peak stress of specimen, the stress concentration occurs in some crosslinking sites, due to the void, molecular structure singularity under stressed and even some inclusion et al. Once crosslinking sites break, then more molecular chain units are freed which are previously constrained by these sites. Then the chain segments are formed by those freed chain units, and start to motion due to the external loads. The breaking of crosslinking sites and the coordinated motion of more chain units join in the cooperative deformation, and then the deformation resistance of specimen will be weakening, and result in strain softening phenomenon in macroscopic view. With the specimen further deformation, some of the residual crosslinking sites are stressed to break due to the same factor. Then it induces the further weakening, namely continuous strain softening. Overall, with the breakage of more crosslinking sites, the more chain units are freed from these sites, and they form

more chain segments to join into the molecular chain cooperative motion, and present continuous strain softening characteristic in stress-strain curve.

Figure 6 Deformation and microstructure evolution process of nanocomposite.

The crosslinking sites still happen in the plateau stress region. This conclusion can be drawn based on the different specific modulus $E_{s5}=0.69$ in Figure 5 (A), and $E_{s10}=0.58$ in Figure 5 (B). For the below peak stress experiments, the specimen deformed into the plateau stress region, with true strain 0.220 in the fourth test, whereas the larger deformation happened on the specimen in beyond peak experiment with true strain up to 0.245 in the ninth test. Larger deformation results in the specific modulus drop sharper in the tenth test. By virtue of the dependence of the cross-linked degree and elastic modulus, it is predicted that the residual crosslinking sites still continue to break due to the same factor in plateau stress deformation. In mechanical viewpoint, the physical entanglement acts the same role as chemical crosslinking sites in the curves, since their disentanglement/destruction due to the stress concentration also free neighboring chain units, facilitating chain segments motion for subsequent strain softening.

4.3 CNT conductive network

The mechanism is predicted for the matrix epoxy of nanocomposite that the cross-linked sites are about to break when the specimen is loaded to peak stress, and the more molecular chain units freed from the broken sites can form the molecular segments to cooperative motion of molecular microstructure. Accordingly, the conductive network of CNT is partly destroyed, and then some conductive passageways are interrupted. Furthermore, the second electrical conductivity mechanism: electron hopping will be partly limited. Due to the sites' breakage, the distance between CNTs will widen. Then the resistivity will increase distinctly due to its high dependence of electron hopping on the separation distance between CNTs [24]. Thus, the resistivity will start to sharply increase since the peak strain as shown in Fig. 2 (C). With further deformation, the networks are destroyed more and more. The resistivity continues to grow. For below peak stress tests specimen, the resistivity presents linearly increase. This is explained by the inner deformation mechanisms of material: the short chain compositions such as valence angles and other tiny chain units, start to coordinate motions. These won't destroy the carbon nanotube conductive network, thus the resistivity changes gradually due to the limitation of electron hopping. The interface debonding between CNT and epoxy hardly occurs at this deformation region, and has a little influence on the resistivity due to the strong interface strength, and so does the fracture of CNT [24-27]. For the in-situ electrical-mechanical measurement, repeating tests are conducted on CNT composite for more than 3 times, and the fitted slopes of the resistivity after and before peak strain are in a nearly fixed proportion: 2.78 ± 0.095 .

9 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the paper reports the measurement results of the CNT modified composite and matrix pure epoxy in the aspect of electrical or mechanical behaviors. The volume resistivity increases with the strain growing. The abrupt resistivity increase happens at the peak stress. It facilitates the prediction of the deformation mechanism for epoxy, with the aim of the mechanic confirmation of specifically-designed experiments: the crosslinking sites start to break and initiate the strain-softening

deformation, which induces the abrupt increase of material resistivity. The mechanism is also further confirmed by gap stress, peak strain and CNT conductive network. Such a mechanism bridges the previous consensus on the microstructure evolution of below and post peak stress deformation of epoxy, and also modifies the nature of molecular chain segment motion. The findings about the mechanism and the resistivity of CNT composites would be helpful for the design and optimization of pure epoxy and nanocomposites with desirable mechanical/electrical properties, and damage monitoring and smart structures.

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